

**ANALYSIS OF THE EDUCATIONAL MANIFESTATION OF
ORIGINAL PEOPLES AND THE EXPERIENCE OF INDIGENOUS
CHILDREN ACCORDING TO THE CONCEPT OF CITIZENSHIP IN
RELATION TO TEACHING IN URBAN SCHOOLS IN THE CITY OF
PARICONHA-AL**

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this article is to explore the current situation of urban and indigenous education in the municipality of Pariconha-AL, based on knowledge and research. The arguments presented are linked to theories and interviews carried out in the municipality, covering three types of education: Indigenous Education in two schools in different villages, Primary Education in the municipal network and Secondary Education in the state network. In addition, the article provides information on unprecedented experiences of what happens in an indigenous school, detailing its village-oriented educational process. Interviews were conducted with staff from the other educational institutions, broadening local knowledge and contributing to an understanding of the current conditions of coexistence. Even in a small municipality, social inclusion still faces challenges, and cultural discrimination persists. The article addresses this concept, comparing urban and indigenous education in the current social context, using theoretical approaches from relevant works. The overall aim is to expose both the theoretical knowledge and the information provided by the interviewees, establishing a timeline that covers past and present developments in the local educational scene.

Keywords: Education; Native peoples; Differentiated education; Public education.

INTRODUCTION

This article's main objective is to expose the theoretical knowledge and field research carried out by the author. The research was conducted in a small municipality whose history dates back to the 19th century, with the arrival of four families – Teodósio, Viana, Vieira and Felix –, who began settlement in Carabeiras dos Teodósios, on the banks of the Moxotó River.

Later, an indigenous community known as Pankararu also established itself in the region, migrating from the municipality of Tacaratu-PE to Pariconha-AL.

The development of the municipality included the formation of villages, such as Jeripankó, originating from the migration of the Pankararu. The history and growth of Pariconha led the author to reflect on educational development, covering public and indigenous schools. Two public schools at the headquarters, Escola Municipal de Educação Básica Padre Epifânio Moura and Escola Estadual de Educação Básica de Pariconha, were included, as well as two indigenous schools, Escola Indígena José Carapina and Escola Estadual Indígena Juvino Henrique da Silva.

The objective of the work is to elaborate and expose the daily life of the urban and indigenous communities of Pariconha, comparing and analyzing the educational regulations of each community. The focus is on understanding the development and social contribution of each person, considering the challenges faced by society. The municipality, with a population of 10,546 inhabitants, has a significant indigenous portion, representing 56.12% of the population.

The research was conducted through visits to educational institutions, both urban and indigenous, adequately exploring knowledge through interviews with school directors. The work incorporates theoretical knowledge and experiences from other authors related to common curricular education and indigenous education.

CULTURE AND EDUCATION

The term "culture" is complex and can be approached in different ways, being studied both anthropologically and in other fields of knowledge. Anthropologically, culture is understood as the set of knowledge, beliefs, values, practices, customs, art, morals, laws and other capabilities and habits acquired by human beings as a member of a society. In this context, culture is dynamic and constantly changing.

Symbolism, in turn, refers to the use of symbols to represent ideas, concepts or meanings. Symbols are elements that have culturally attributed meaning and are used to express and communicate values, beliefs and identities. This concept is related to symbolic anthropology, which explores the role of symbols in the construction of social reality.

Urbanism, on the other hand, is associated with the study and planning of cities and the way people interact in the urban environment. It addresses issues such as urban design, the organization of space, urban mobility and social dynamics in cities. The formation of social

groups and cultural diversification are often linked to the urban context, where different people and communities coexist and interact.

In this way, culture, symbolism and urbanism are interconnected concepts, and understanding how these elements intertwine can provide a more comprehensive view of the complexity of society and human relationships.

In his thoughts Laraia emphasizes his anthropological point of view as follows:

Anthropologists are completely convinced that genetic differences are not determinants of cultural differences. According to Felix Keesing, “there is no significant correlation between the distribution of genetic characters and the distribution of cultural behaviors. Any normal human child can be educated in any culture if placed from the beginning in a suitable learning situation.” (LARAIA, 1986)

Analysis of the historical context of Brazilian education is crucial to understanding the origins and evolution of the educational system in the country. During colonization, as mentioned, access to education was restricted, mainly intended for the children of colonial elites. Enslaved people, indigenous people and other marginalized social groups were excluded from this right.

Colonization focused on the economic exploitation and catechization of indigenous people, without prioritizing the educational training of the population in general. This dynamic continued for a long period, contributing to educational inequalities.

The turn towards a more public and accessible education for all occurred with the promulgation of the 1946 Constitution, which established fundamental principles for teaching in the country. This was an important milestone in the search for democratization of access to education in Brazil.

However, even with advances over time, persistent challenges such as regional, social and ethnic inequality still affect the Brazilian educational system. Understanding this historical trajectory is essential to discuss and implement more inclusive and egalitarian educational policies.

According to Gonçalves' analysis,

Since the 1930s, several documents generated at national and international meetings or events, with the participation of government representatives or professionals working in the field of cultural heritage, recommended educational actions that presupposed the existence of a collection of cultural assets to be protected. Educational actions, in this context, would form part of preservation policies: they would disseminate the collection, reaffirm its importance, legitimize government bodies responsible for its protection and

collaborate to integrate parts of civil society in the defense of cultural heritage. (GONÇALVES, 2014)

Anísio Teixeira played a fundamental role in the fight for the universalization of education in Brazil, being one of the precursors of the public education system. His work contributed to the implementation of more inclusive and accessible educational policies.

The 1988 Federal Constitution, in its article 205, highlights education as a right for everyone and a duty of the State and the family, highlighting the importance of parents' participation in the education of their children. This integrated vision of education as a collective responsibility is fundamental to building a more just and egalitarian society.

As for New Secondary Education, its approach to integrating professional courses aims to prepare young people for the job market, offering options aligned to their skills and interests. However, it is important to monitor how these changes effectively impact the quality of education and equity of opportunities.

In the context of indigenous institutions, a differentiated and contextualized approach to education is essential to preserve the cultures and traditions of these peoples. The 1988 Constitution recognizes the right of indigenous peoples to specific, quality education. The National Education Plan (PNE) also seeks to guide Indigenous Education according to the needs and characteristics of these communities.

The reference to catechization during the colonization process highlights an important historical aspect, highlighting how educational practices were interconnected with colonial and missionary interests. This historical understanding is crucial to contextualize current educational policies and reflect on challenges and achievements over time. In this context, according to Oliveira,

Until the end of the colonial period, Indigenous Education remained the responsibility of Catholic missionaries of different orders, by tacit or explicit delegation from the Portuguese Crown. With the advent of the Empire, in 1822, everything remained as before: in the Constitutional Project of 1823, in its title XIII, art. 254, the creation of "...establishments for the Catechesis and civilization of the Indians..." was proposed. As the Constitution of 1824 was silent on this point, the Additional Act of 1834, art. 11, paragraph 5, sought to correct the "gap", and attributed competence to the Provincial Legislative Assemblies to promote cumulatively with the General Assemblies and Governments "...the catechesis and civilization of the indigenous people and the establishment of colonies". This device can be considered the legal ancestor of Decree No. 26/91, in force, which promotes the decentralization (stateization and/or municipalization) of indigenous schools. (SILVA, 1994)

The municipalization of indigenous schools, although a practice that occurs in some cases, raises important questions about the preservation of the cultural identity and rights of

indigenous peoples. The implementation of projects that aim to integrate these peoples into mainstream society often faces resistance due to the importance of preserving indigenous traditions, languages and ways of life.

The existence of more than 2,800 indigenous schools registered in Brazil reflects a diversity of contexts and realities faced by these communities. However, municipalization can represent a challenge for the autonomy of these schools and for guaranteeing an education that respects and values cultural particularities.

The attempt to "urbanize" indigenous children raises questions about the imposition of hegemonic cultural standards. Respect for cultural diversity and recognition of indigenous ways of life are fundamental to ensuring education that promotes intercultural understanding and does not subjugate local identities.

Resistance or misunderstanding towards indigenous peoples is often rooted in historical prejudices, stereotypes and lack of knowledge about their cultures and histories. The promotion of citizenship for indigenous children must be based on respect for their cultural identity and the appreciation of their traditions.

Reflection on why indigenous peoples can irritate the Brazilian elite can involve an analysis of historical relationships, disputes over territory, natural resources and power. Overcoming these tensions requires a commitment to social justice, equity and respect for human rights.

In short, indigenous education must be sensitive to the specific needs of these communities, respecting and strengthening their identities, languages and traditions, without imposing external cultural models. This contributes to a more inclusive and plural society.

According to Oliveira's view, he expresses in his text the following thought

The vast majority of Indigenous Education programs underway or being implemented in our country seem to turn their backs on the constitutional articles mentioned above. For this panorama to undergo a substantial change, it would be necessary, first of all, as the anthropologist Araci Lopes da Silva very well pointed out in a recent work (1993), to promote educational campaigns that aim to combat ignorance and prejudice regarding to indigenous peoples. Campaigns that target not only civil society, but mainly the public sector (federal, state and municipal), unfortunately still without an adequate understanding of the issue. (SILVA, 1994)

The issue of integrating indigenous children into urban schools is, in fact, a challenge that involves several dimensions, such as prejudice, bullying and the lack of adequate historical contextualization. Brazilian cultural diversity is vast, and schools play a crucial role in promoting respect and understanding between different ethnicities.

The lack of methodological cultural teachings contextualized in the history of Brazil can contribute to the perpetuation of stereotypes and prejudices. The historical approach often does not adequately reflect the ethnic diversity of the country, and this can lead to a limited and distorted understanding of indigenous cultures.

The globalized view of ethnicities, when devalued, harms not only the integration of indigenous children in urban schools, but also the construction of a more inclusive and respectful society. Education plays a key role in deconstructing stereotypes and promoting intercultural understanding.

Teachers have the crucial responsibility of offering an education that goes beyond the basics, exploring the richness of Brazilian cultural diversity. Encouraging discussion about the contributions of indigenous peoples to the formation of Brazil, their traditions, languages and ways of life is essential to combat prejudice and promote respect.

Furthermore, it is essential to create inclusive school environments, where difference is valued and celebrated. Anti-bullying strategies, educational programs about diversity and the promotion of activities that highlight the cultural contributions of different groups can be effective tools for building a more harmonious coexistence among children.

Open and constant dialogue with the school community, including parents, students and teachers, is essential to face these challenges and build a more fair and equitable education for all.

INTERVIEWS WITH INDIGENOUS AND PUBLIC EDUCATION PROFESSIONALS FROM THE CITY OF PARICONHA-AL

Interviews were carried out related to the theme of this article for knowledge purposes, namely, in public institutions in the headquarters of Pariconha-AL, the Escola Municipal de Educação Básica Padre Epifânio Moura and the Escola Estadual de Educação Básica de Pariconha and in indigenous institutions, Escola Indígena José Carapina and the Juvino Henrique da Silva Indigenous State School.

The first institution interviewed was the Escola Municipal de Educação Básica Padre Epifânio Moura, located in the Auto da Boa Vista neighborhood in the city of Pariconha-AL, the available interviewee was the director of the institution, Lucineide Araújo. Lucineide reports that she has been director of this institution for 6 months, considering that her experience has been challenging, but so far, she is working in harmony for the students' academic success. The institution is based on approximately 622 students enrolled, including ethnic students and

according to its experience, the educational development of the institution is going well, according to it, the help of committed teachers speeds up the teaching-learning process. In addition to offering education in the regular classroom, the school provides AEE – Specialized Educational Assistance. The learning process of these students takes place a little slowly, but each advance is a very rewarding satisfaction for the students.

During the interview I asked if there are educational projects for primary education I and II and the interviewee replied yes and that they are integrated projects, aiming to meet the needs of each student, taking into account the levels of reading and writing learning. In this way, with the evolution of pedagogical projects, the institution maintains a good relationship with the community, as a school they strive to contribute to the benefit of all, considering that there are projects and actions that involve parents in school education of the student's life.

At one point I asked director Luciana about her opinion on having indigenous institutions in the Pariconha-AL region and she responded that she believes there is a desire to rescue and maintain local culture.

The second interview was carried out at the Escola Estadual de Educação Básica de Pariconha located in the city center, which offers secondary education, the interviewee this time was Paulo José do Nascimento, he has been a teacher for around 20 years, where he initially worked with a teaching elementary school, later he began to work with the secondary level gradually, starting a series each year for a while he was a manager at the secondary school and currently works as a teaching coordinator. The school has approximately 450 students, including students from other ethnicities, but he finds it relevant and necessary to have indigenous schools in the municipality, given the need for people to keep their customs and traditions alive.

The coordinator Paulo believes that educational development has improved significantly, according to him, they had almost no infrastructure, as there were very few technological resources and in many cases they released teachers in certain areas of knowledge while today they have a full complement of teachers. graduates in their areas debts. From this, the interviewee replied that the school offers some projects through the education department, such as the mentor project in which teachers act in a more meaningful and relevant way, seeking strategies with updated methodologies to achieve greater student performance. Also the school 10 project , which aims to keep the student at school in which a sum of money is deposited so that the student maintains attendance, among others. Although the institution establishes projects for students, the interviewee responds that so far it does not offer projects that directly involve parents.

The school promotes several moments of listening and meetings with the community, such as the parent-teacher meeting that takes place every two months. They also offer pedagogical sessions, in addition to virtual communication channels with groups on WhatsApp, among others.

During the interview, the coordinator was asked if the school had special education and he replied yes, the school has a teacher responsible for special education, in addition to a class assistant who works with students who have a report that are included in room and they have individualized monitoring with the schedule previously formulated by the special education teacher.

The third interview was carried out at the educational institution Escola Indígena José Carapina, located in the Ouricuri village established in the Jeripankó village in the municipality of Pariconha-AL. The interviewee in turn was Cícero Pereira dos Santos, professor of Jiripanko Indigenous culture and sociology, he has a degree in Social Anthropology from UFAL/ics. Cícero reports that he has been in indigenous school education for 20 years, his experience consists of working on education that guarantees access to school from a legal and contextual point of view. The challenge is to keep the indigenous school powerful within the system that treats education as a whole while they defend teaching more within reality.

The school has just over 300 students, from pre-school to high school. Indigenous school education is not a reality if it is established in villages. According to the professor, “Alagoas does not guarantee the exercise of education as a whole. Schools have suffered from curriculums decontextualized by the system, which leads to losses when we need to guarantee the rights of our students according to the legislation. So we have made small advances since institutional thinking is still not respected.” The institution follows Seduc's guidelines, but they prioritize knowledge contextualized between the curriculum and the social, cultural and traditional experiences of its people. By doing the curriculum in reverse, this way all subjects are subject to adjustments and assimilable to the reality of my people.

The institution has projects articulated by Seduc in the area of technology, according to him technology is an important tool, the institution has a computer laboratory which has helped with the issue of digital inclusion, but the school does not have professionals in the area to make use of it. with more income. However, students have improved in accessing new information related to the subjects. Professor Cícero replaces the answer with a significant disadvantage, “I do not consider that there was any learning, the delay in the contents programmed by Seduc and manages, were just to fulfill a schedule for the school year and, with weak planning, it overloaded coordinators, managers and teachers who they did not obtain good results and this

was not exclusive to our school. I believe that the system needed to work more on the role of families in the process instead of placing everything solely in the hands of the school.”

Regarding the question of whether there is a relationship between the institution and the community of Pariconha, Cícero responded that it is “Non-existent. Even though there is legislation that obliges municipalities to expand their curriculum to enhance cultural and interethnic education, Pariconha does not perform this function. All indigenous schools in the state are state-run, they receive resources from the state and the MEC, without any incentive from the municipality.” When asked about special education at the institution, the interviewee reported that they only received professionals in the area this year, but the lack of infrastructure stopped the exercise of the function.

Regarding the interviewee's opinion on having indigenous education in the municipality of Pariconha, the interviewee responds, “we don't have to worry about that, my people are a legally independent society from the municipality. I do not consider that we are a school within the municipality, since there is no influence between the parties other than friendly treatment”.

Regarding High School Reform, the interviewee responded, “chaos. Our schools are not ready either in terms of physical structure or personnel for what the new pre-secondary education says, but I believe that the biggest harm is in not including indigenous school education with more emphasis as the constitution says. Thought was given to the student's freedom of being, but their right to time to learn was not guaranteed, nor were they guaranteed the necessary conditions for this.”

And regarding the prejudice they may suffer from, Professor Cícero responds that, according to him, the indigenous school itself is already a target for prejudice.

Finally, the fourth and final interview took place at the Juvino Henrique da Silva Indigenous State School, the interviewee is Tais Lima, she has been coordinator of the institution since 2019, her experience as an indigenous school coordinator has always been instigated, as at all times Those who work with indigenous education always come across challenging themes and in addition to the challenges of indigenous schools, there is also the collective challenge in relation to Brazilian indigenous peoples. The indigenous pedagogical coordinator faces issues that go beyond the role of the coordinator, as he or she has a role that is different from what is traditional, cultural and what belongs to the people, in short, everything that involves the Katokinn people.

The Juvino Henrique da Silva Indigenous State School is located in the Katokinn Village established in the Alto da Boa Vista neighborhood in the city of Pariconha-AL. The institution itself is currently experiencing some instabilities in the structure of the building, even though

the State turns a blind eye to the current condition, teachers continue to fight not to give up on differentiated education. The lack of a more collective space ends up interrupting educational development as an institution. The school currently has 223 students from kindergarten to high school. The institution is always developing educational projects in which students must start from early childhood education and which branch out to high school, according to the coordinator, “we have an articulation, between us coordinators. Both in elementary school and high school education and in the Coordination of early childhood and elementary school education, we try to maintain unity in what we are developing within the school so that there are no distortions in learning and so that everyone is covered by a certain theme”. The school also promotes projects for parents, which are identified as workshops in the traditional part and workshops developed at strategic moments in the year, where families are invited to participate in the school as partners. Parents always visit the school and are always asked to attend so that they can talk and participate in pedagogical strategies for their children's education.

The institution, having a different structure, still faces a lot of prejudice from some people in the pariconhence community. The structure of the institution can sometimes be used as an annex to the subject to belittle indigenous education and classify it as low quality education. In its 11th generation, the Juvino Henrique da Silva Indigenous State School has an excellent position compared to other schools, which means that even if the structure is not adequate, education is provided with excellence.

Regarding education for children with disabilities, the interviewee states that, as there is no adequate structure in the institution, it is not possible to have a special room. As there is no special, these children are placed with other students in the classroom accompanied by a classroom assistant and regarding the development of these children, the interviewee reports that it has been satisfactory, as they are able to be among their peers. It is important to inquire about the following statement by coordinator Tais, “we even have autistic students in early childhood education who can already read fluently and this is a great achievement for us”. The projects for these children are produced based on inclusion, so the school strives to ensure that the projects are as inclusive as possible. According to the interviewee, “I believe producing an inclusion project means excluding these children!”

Regarding indigenous education in the municipality of Pariconha-AL, the interviewee reports that it is a benefit among the people and enriches the Pariconhence culture, as indigenous education is a symbol of resistance.

During the experiences covered by the interviews with education professionals, I found it interesting to also try to interview the chief of the Katokinn village to find out his point of

view regarding the education of his villagers. The chief in question, Daniel, entered the village as chief last year after the tragic death of his aunt known as Nina Cacique, one of the most warrior women imaginable.

The Katokinn village is itself a branch of the Pankararu of Tacaratu-PE. Its origin and emancipation took place in 2001 by a group led by the shaman Arvilino and Maria das Graças, claiming ethnicity.

Finally, when interviewing the chief, he said with his words that indigenous education is a way for people to work within their own indigenous community without distorting the culture, according to him “the history book tells the entire history of Brazil distorted with small lies saying that there are only indigenous people in the Amazon giving an indigenous profile and our school is already used for that, to show our own students that there are indigenous people everywhere and it is also a means of showing our cultures to be practiced and being kept in books and stories”.

Regarding his vision regarding education being municipalized, he says it is a total loss for the indigenous community. Chief Daniel portrays that, “it will be the same way as it was during the colonization of Brazil, they took our customs and removed and added religion and with that we are increasingly losing our customs because within the school it will not be valued, it will causing loss and over time with the death of shamans or elders and fighting warriors, it ends and distorts all communities. That’s why municipalized education cannot be accepted, because it could harm communities.” Chief Daniel reports that he studied in a public school and that in his experience as a student he was the target of prejudice from both students and teachers in the municipal education network. made him uncomfortable, he reports that he was already failed due to absences because there were cultural events in the village and he could not miss it so as not to harm his customs, from this report it is clear that public education, even if it does not encourage it, stands in defense of non-indigenous support. At the time when Daniel was a public school student, the Katokinn village did not yet have an institution.

In terms of supporting bodies, he mentioned APOINME and PIBES, they are indigenous organizations that defend and support indigenous education.

And regarding the difficulties in bringing education to the indigenous community, the chief reports that the main difficulty comes from the community itself, according to him, “generally the schools in the indigenous community are attached schools and these attachments are donated by the people themselves. indigenous people and the majority of parents do not take their children out of the comfort of the air conditioning to put them in a school that does not even have a fan and the other difficulty lies with the State, which is providing a quality

school, is providing an improvement and it does not. This path leaves the community to pursue it on its own, then you have to put pressure on the Federal State, you have to call the governors, you have to call the public ministry and Gere.”

The current manager of the municipality of Pariconha-AL was contacted to be included in the research, however, for health reasons it was impossible to access it, both in person and remotely. We also looked for ways to contact the chief of the Jeripankó village, but I was unsuccessful in the search.

CONCLUSION

It is clear that Brazilian education needs to evolve in prioritizing historical contextualization, providing a more comprehensive and respectful understanding of the country's cultural diversity. Tackling prejudice, especially in school environments, is a crucial task that demands actions at both the individual and institutional levels.

Chief Daniel's reports highlight the persistence of prejudice, indicating the need for a more open and inclusive approach on the part of educators. Teacher training must include specific strategies for dealing with cultural diversity, promoting respect and mutual understanding.

The fight for the rights of indigenous peoples continues, and education plays a central role in this process. Educational projects developed by these communities have demonstrated not only resilience in the face of prejudice, but also the ability to offer significant contributions to global knowledge.

The presence of foreign researchers in the villages highlights the importance of indigenous knowledge not only for Brazil, but also for the international scene. This visibility can contribute to the recognition and appreciation of the cultural riches present in the municipality of Pariconha.

The city's growth and development offer opportunities to explore and preserve local cultural riches, promoting knowledge both among local inhabitants and in academia. Collaboration between the community, researchers and educational institutions can contribute to the construction of a more inclusive, fair and diversity-conscious society.

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